

TIAGoGPT: Exploring the Potential of LLMs in TIAGo Robot-Assisted Interventions for Supporting Children with Social Skill Difficulties

Dissertation Project Report

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Declaration

The candidate confirms that the work submitted is his own and that appropriate credit has been given where reference has been made to the work of others. The candidate agrees that this report can be electronically checked for plagiarism.

Charles Mfon Anjah

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Abstract

The TIAGo robot is one of the outstanding robots in the research field. As a research-purposed robot, TIAGo is equipped with enormous features that, over time, have led to some groundbreaking achievements. From path planning with self-collision avoidance, multi-language text-to-speech, facial and speech recognition, and telepresence to teleoperation with leap motion sensors as an assistive intervention in healthcare and as personalised home assistance, given the rapid growth in robotics and AI, such as humanoids, it is important to access the TIAGo relevance in research. In this project, the TIAGo capability is being explored to assess its ability to adapt seamlessly and respond effectively when used with cutting-edge LLMs for a modern-world scenario, such as supporting children with social skills difficulties. The project showcased TIAGo as an assistive robot incorporating cutting-edge LLM technologies such as whisper and GPT-3.5-turbo models through a dedicated and innovative system called "TIAGoGPT". This dedicated platform provided personalised support with the user's speech passing through a voice recording and processing module to the models, with the voice response being sounded through the robot's output device, such as speakers. The system models were fine-tuned to suit their application, and the entire TIAGoGPT platform was built with a robust data security and privacy framework to ensure that the highest ethical standards are upheld. The results obtained from different users during the levels of testing showed a considerable high confidence rate in the system. This attests to the effectiveness and efficiency of the TIAGo robot and the promises it holds as an assistive measure in transforming interventions provided to children, especially those with social skills difficulties.

Keywords: *TIAGo robot, GPT-3, LLM, Automatic Speech Recognition, Robot-Assisted Intervention, Social-skill Difficulties, Child support, Interactive, TIAGoGPT, whisper.*

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Glossary of Terms

Abbreviation	Full Description
ABA	Applied Behaviour Analysis
ADHD	Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Audio Recording
ARE	Augmented Reality for Education
ASD	Autism Spectrum Disorders
ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
CA	Conversational Agent
CAE	Child Advocacy and Empowerment
CLARA	Clever Automated Robot Application
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CTRL	Control Key on the computer keyboard
DSAL	Data Storage and Analysis Layer
GLP	Gamified Learning Platforms
GPT	Generative Pre-trained Transformer
GUI	Graphic User Interface
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HDMI	High-Definition Multimedia Interface
HMM	Hidden Markov Models
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCPL	Language and Cognitive Processing Layer
LLM	Large Language Model
LM	Language Model
LSEP	Legal, Social, Ethical, and Professional
LSEPI	LSEP Issues
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
MV	Model-View
MVC	Model-View-Controller framework
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NVLD	Non-Verbal Learning Disability

OS	Operating System
RADI	Robotic Assistive Diagnostic Intervention
RAII	Robotic Assistive Interactive Intervention
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAT	Robot-Assisted Therapy
RATI	Robotic Assistive Therapeutic Intervention
RET	Robot-Enhanced Therapy
ROL	Robot Output Layer
SAR	Socially Assistive Robotics
SARI	Socially Assistive Robotics Intervention
SCD	Social Communication Disorder
SPL	Speech Processing Layer
SSD	Solid State Drive
SVM	Support Vector Machines
TIAGo	Take-It-And-Go
TIAGoGPT	Take-It-And-Go Generative Pre-trained Transformer
TLPL	Tonal Language Processing Layer
TTS	Text-To-Speech
UI	User Interface
UIL	User Input Layer
USA	United State of America
USB	Universal Serial Board
VRT	Virtual Reality Therapy
VS	Virtual Studio

1.0 Introduction

Child support, the focal principle of child advocacy and empowerment (CAE), encompasses a multifaceted and compassionate approach to addressing the diverse challenges and needs that children may encounter with the aim of developing their strengths, resilience, and self-determination, enabling them to thrive and reach their full potentials (Popliger, Toste and Heath, 2009). The conventional approaches like the social skills training, educational and school-based support, creative and play therapies, support groups, etc. (Smart et al., 2016) has witness great strength in promoting children's well-being.

However, as the complexity of modern-day challenges faced by children continues to grow (Thulin et al., 2020), traditional approaches to intervention may not always be sufficient that has led to a growing interest in exploring innovative ways to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of support and assistance for children facing various challenges and needs in recent years (van Heerden et al., 2020). The primary difference between these methods and the conventional ones is their greater adaptability and wide variety of support capabilities, which addresses the accessibility issues encountered with the previous (Smart et al., 2016). The innovative methods include virtual reality therapy (VRT), gamified learning platforms (GLP), telehealth services, augmented reality for education (ARE) (Silvera-Tawil et al., 2022), mobile apps, robotics-assisted interventions (RAI), and AI-driven personalised education among others (LaGasse, 2014). One of such exciting avenues that has gained traction is the integration of advanced robotic and AI technologies into assistive interventions (Vemprala et al., 2023; Varaprasad Janamala et al., 2023), which give some feelings of connection to the user (Katsanis and Moulianitis, 2020).

The integration of advanced technologies, such as large language models (LLMs), with robotic systems has ushered in a new era of innovative possibilities in various domains. Research has shown that robot-assisted interventions hold great promise for engaging children, fostering social development, and enhancing learning experiences (Katsanis and Moulianitis, 2020; Lee et al., 2012; Krithiga 2019). The application of robotics in assistive contexts has already demonstrated significant benefits, particularly for children with attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), autism spectrum disorders (ASD), non-verbal learning disability (NVLD), social communication disorder (SCD), developmental delays, and various emotional and cognitive needs which represent to a great extend the social skills difficulties among children (Srinivasan et al., 2015; Jain et al., 2020; Cao et al., 2019).

Among these remarkable robotic technologies, take-it-and-go (TIAGo) robot stands out as a promising companion capable of revolutionising the way we interact (Muscar and Grama, 2022) and

support children most specifically, with social skill difficulties. Path planning with self-collision avoidance, multi-language text-to-speech, facial and speech recognition, telepresence, and teleoperation with leap motion sensor are the features considered in much research (Ling, Liu, and Tian, 2020; Hassan et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2023). It becomes more interactive when the technology is incorporated with large language AI models (LLMs) (Ma et al., 2023; openai.com, 2023; Wang et al., 2023; Chang et al., 2023) such as the recent generative pretrained transformer (GPT-3 or GPT-4) models from OpenAI sources (OpenAI, 2023b; Floridi and Chiriatti, 2020) where communication between human and the robot can be in natural language (Wake et al., 2023).

1.1. Problem Statement

There are growing research areas as more are added. There are also research areas that have common objectives and act as a merger. Such is the integration of advanced technologies, such as Large Language Models (LLMs), with robotic systems, ushering in a new era of innovative possibilities in various domains. This project delves into the promising domain of using LLMs within TIAGo robot as assistive interventions to address a critical aspect of child development: social skill difficulties in children (Szymona et al., 2021). Addressing a range of neurodevelopmental challenges, including verbal expression, behavioural patterns, social attention, and comprehension (Varaprasad Janamala et al., 2023), which are essential for social communication and relationship formation.

One step towards achieving this was the development of AudioGPT software by Wake, N., et al. (2023), using the functionality of ChatGPT with traditional speech recognition systems that use foundational models in natural language processing. The accuracy and efficiency of the implemented system were greatly impacted by the flaws in those models. However, the envisioned system seeks to tap into the cognitive capabilities of LLMs, which have demonstrated remarkable advancements in understanding and generating human language across diverse contexts. By incorporating LLMs into the TIAGo robotic platform, this project aspires to create a dynamic and adaptive intervention tool that can assist children in developing and enhancing their social interaction skills. This project not only aligns with the growing interest in human-robot collaboration but also addresses a pressing societal concern by focusing on the unique needs of children who require specialised support.

As a result, the project seeks to leverage the power of LLMs in conjunction with the versatile TIAGo robot to explore how these interventions can offer a novel approach to aiding children facing social skill challenges by utilising state-of-the-art AI technologies such as voice transcription (with the Whisper large-v2 model), generative text response (with the GPT3.5-turbo model) (Huang, R. et al., 2023), and text synthesis (with Google Cloud Text-to-Speech model) capabilities. Obviously, by improving their communication skills, emotional well-being, and overall quality of life, a positive impact on the target population and a contribution to the field of robotic-assisted interventions would have been achieved.

1.2. Research Motivation

This research is motivated by the desire to leverage recent advancements in LLMs for practical robotic-assisted interventions, specifically aimed at providing support for children's social skills. This motivation sets to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of interventions, ultimately benefiting children in need of social skill support. It embarks on a pioneering journey, merging the capabilities of LLMs and the TIAGo robot to create an innovative intervention system.

1.3. Research Aim

The aim of this research is to explore the potential of state-of-the-art technologies such as Whisper, GPT-3.5-turbo, and GoogleCloud Text-to-Speech (TTS) embodied in the TIAGo robot for the development and implementation of a user-friendly robotic platform that eliminates communication difficulties in children, consequently improving their interactive skills. The system aims to utilize voice transcription, generative text response, and text synthesis capabilities to create a reliable, personalized, and contextually relevant response within the TIAGo robot for supporting children.

The personalized response generator using GPT-3 technology, which provides tailored responses, aims to establish an effective and engaging conversational experience between the TIAGo robot, acting as a conversational agent (CA), and children with social skill difficulties, promoting improved communication and social interaction abilities in a supportive and interactive environment.

Additionally, to boost user trust throughout the system's usability testing, the project intends to use a development approach with an emphasis on the ethical value of data privacy, security, and user permission. These objectives are stated below. Lastly, the project hopes to improve the target population's communication abilities, emotional health, and general quality of life while also contributing to the area of robotic-assisted interventions.

1.4. Research Objectives

The research-specific objectives are:

1. To develop a voice recording module that effectively records only human spoken prompts.
2. To develop a robust and reliable voice transcription module that accurately converts spoken prompts into text format using the Whisper large-v2 model.
3. To implement a response generation module utilising the generative pretrained transformer model (GPT-3.5-turbo) to generate appropriate and contextually relevant responses based on the transcription input.
4. To integrate the Google Text-to-Speech model to synthesise the generated responses into natural-sounding speech.

5. To design a user-friendly graphic interface to facilitate seamless interaction and the display of generated responses.
6. To implement a 6-step data security and privacy framework with a consent mechanism for users' data protection.
7. To deploy the developed TIAGoGPT system onto the TIAGo Lite robot.
8. To evaluate and test the TIAGoGPT deployed on the TIAGo Lite robot.

1.5. Research Scope

This research explores the realm of robotic-assisted interventions, specifically using the TIAGo robot and LLMs AI-driven technologies, to address social skills difficulties in children. The focus is on providing support and assistance, not on symptoms detection or therapeutic interventions.

1.6. Existing Systems Using TIAGo Audio Capabilities

The TIAGo manipulation task has witnessed greater attention in recent years, particularly within healthcare environments, to enhance patient care and alleviate the workload of medical staff. But a closer look at the quantum of research work that focuses on the audio capabilities of this robot shows that more attention needs to be paid to that angle. In a study conducted by Muscar and Grama (2022), which is one of the few research projects done in this area, they explored the application of service robots in hospitals, focusing on the TIAGo robot. They proposed an innovative approach that combines Moving Picture Experts Group-7 (MPEG-7) features with Hidden Markov Models (HMM) to enable the TIAGo robot to comprehend contextual information through audio signals. This integration empowered the robot to function as a medical assistant, thereby reducing person-to-person interactions and contributing to the enhancement of healthcare facilities. Empirical results demonstrated an impressive 96.86% overall classification accuracy during testing, highlighting the efficacy of their framework.

Expanding on this audio signal processing framework of TIAGo was an area considered. As swiftly as one could think, Grama and Rusu (2019) introduced three modular components designed for acoustic analysis in the robot. These modules encompassed tasks such as audio data stream recording, extraction of isolated audio events, development of classification models, and audio event identification. The study employed liftering Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) as the feature set and proposes the use of the k-Nearest Neighbour (kNN) algorithm for classification and identification of audio events. The researchers achieved a remarkable 98.55% accuracy in real-life testing, which showcased the robustness of their approach.

To further enrich the capabilities of the TIAGo robot, Grama et al. (2021) introduced an expanded audio database, encompassing 3300 isolated audio events across 110 distinct classes. This database,

derived from both the TIAGo robot and its simulated counterpart, focused on indoor events in various scenarios. It facilitated the identification of indoor events based on audio signatures, with a specific emphasis on scenarios involving elderly or chronically ill individuals living independently. Also, Grama and Rusu (2018) extended the exploration of the TIAGo robot's capabilities, particularly its ability to respond to tasks initiated through audio signals. The study recorded a specialised audio data stream containing 46 distinct classes of sound events, leveraging LPC, LPCC, and MFCC features. The researchers experimented with various classifiers, ultimately favouring Support Vector Machines (SVM) and kNN for their reliability and computational efficiency. They concluded that MFCC coefficients are optimal for feature extraction. This result reaffirmed the suitability of these components in audio-based robotic interactions.

Collectively, these studies highlighted the progressive evolution of the TIAGo service robot's audio capabilities, from its integration of audio context comprehension to its advanced acoustic analysis modules and expanded audio database. These advancements contributed to its role as a medical assistant, providing valuable support in healthcare settings and other contexts where audio-based interactions are pivotal. As the field continues to develop, the TIAGo robot stands as a testament to the potential of technology in enhancing human-robot interactions and improving overall quality of life.

1.7. Novelty Innovation and Challenges

The landscape of AI-driven human-computer interaction is rapidly evolving, with recent advancements addressing the limitations of existing models while introducing novel approaches to enhance user experience and practical applicability. Huang et al. (2023) among others took a pioneering leap by introducing AudioGPT, a multi-modal AI system that serves as a complementary innovation to conventional LLMs. Recognising the prowess of LLMs in various domains, the authors identify their shortcomings in complex audio processing and spoken conversations. AudioGPT emerged as a solution, adeptly navigated intricate audio information, and bridged the gap in understanding and generation tasks. Central to its design is an ingenious input/output interface featuring automatic speech recognition (ASR) and Text-to-Speech (TTS) capabilities, thus enabling seamless spoken dialogues akin to virtual assistants like Siri or Alexa. The authors meticulously detailed the architecture and intricacies of AudioGPT, showcased its proficiency in handling AI tasks involving speech, music, and sound. Moreover, it displayed prowess in generating content for interactive talking heads, unlocking new possibilities for diverse audio content creation. This significant stride in human-AI interaction heralded a new era of cooperative content generation and cemented AudioGPT as a pivotal innovation.

Parallely, Wake et al. (2023) harnessed still, the recent breakthroughs in LLMs such as GPT-3 and ChatGPT to amplify the realm of robotics and user experience. Leveraging the innate capabilities of

LLMs, they augmented their potential through an intelligent co-speech gesture generation system. This innovation synergized conceptual context with visual effects, imparting a responsive and immersive dimension to human-robot interaction. The approach enhanced the overall utility of chatbot systems while creating a more engaging and valuable user experience. Also noted was the integration of visual effects into the LLM interface which not only added an appealing aesthetic but also bolstered the technology's utility and applicability. This convergence of language models with gesture generation paved the way for advanced chatbots and interfaces which showcased the synergy between cutting-edge AI advancements and tangible user-centric benefits.

Although Esfandbod et al. (2022) introduced a socially assistive robot, RASA, in speech therapy for children with language disorders, it is important to get intuitive analysis of how the study showcased the robot's potential to enhance engagement and effectiveness in speech therapy sessions, offered a promising avenue for improving language skills in children.

As AI continues to evolve, the developments presented by Huang et al. (2023) and Wake et al. (2023) exemplify the transformative nature of innovation in the field. AudioGPT and the co-speech gesture generation system did not only address critical challenges but also push the boundaries of possibility, presenting novel paradigms for AI-human cooperation and interaction. Likewise, the novel work of Esfandbod et al. (2023). These groundbreaking strides represent a harmonious fusion of technological innovation and human-centric design, propelling AI-driven systems into new realms of capability and utility.

1.8. Research Overview

The report is structured, with each section well-tailored to achieving the project aims and objectives. Just after this section is Chapter 2, which presents a detailed review of the applicable literature and provides an update on the current state of research in robotic-assisted and AI-driven interventions. This is followed by Chapter 3, which gathers and analyses extensively all system requirements, including the software and hardware needed for the proposed robotic-assisted intervention. Chapter 4 focuses on the system's design and implementation, ensuring each part as a unit of the proposed system, when integrated, produces the intended result. Chapter 5 shows the developed TIAGoGPT software testing methodologies adopted and looks at considerations for its deployment as expected. General issues encountered, including the legal, social, ethical, and professional (LSEP), and the key achievements of the designed system are highlighted and discussed extensively in Chapter 6. Finally, Chapter 7 presents conclusions and further perspectives, providing the concluding remarks for the research.

2.0 Literature Review

As research continues to deepen its excavating pace to unravel the continuous complexity and growth of modern-day challenges faced by children, especially those with social skill difficulties, it is evident that traditional approaches to intervention cannot be fully sufficient. Research has also shown that robot-assisted and AI-driven interventions (Xu, Nguyen, and Du, 2023) hold great promise for engaging children, fostering social development, and enhancing learning experiences (Katsanis and Moulitanitis, 2020; Lee et al., 2012; Krithiga, 2019). This chapter presents a review of perspectives detailed in different previous works performed by researchers to find common links as well as the broken ones between them within the development cycle.

2.1. Large language models

Language models had an early birth and were used in applications like the chatbot (Phrasee, 2016) relying primarily on rule-based, bag-of-words-based, and statistical approaches (Jain, Kapur and Dobhal, 2021; Jason Brownlee, 2019;) where word frequency in each training corpus determines the probability of such a word's occurrence (Brown et al., 1992; Huang, 1990). According to Huang (1990), hidden Markov models (HMMs) for language modelling, which are based on the probability of word sequence using hidden states, were used for speech recognition and part-of-speech tagging tasks. This was before the advent of deep learning and neural networks, but they suffered great limitations involving long-range dependency handling, complex linguistic structuring, and semantic relationship capturing (Anjah, 2023). These models also struggled to generalise well to unseen or rare words and phrases (Brown et al., 1992).

LLMs (Ma et al., 2023; Chang et al., 2023) are deep neural networks trained on large human language structures designed with high computational cognitive ability to learn patterns in human language, predict the possible sequence of words, and decode and/or encode new word sequences to form the human natural language (Winiarski et al., 2021; Oota et al., 2023). LLMs have made remarkable progress in recent years (Brown et al., 2020). Presently at the frontline are the bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (BERT) (Devlin et al., 2019), pathways language model (PaLM) (Chowdhery et al., 2022), generative pre-trained transformers v3 (GPT-3) (Floridi and Chiriatti, 2020; Brown et al., 2020), and GPT-4 (OpenAI, 2023a; Chang et al., 2023); more specifically, the GPTs have processing abilities that are seen to be almost at par with human-level natural language performance (OpenAI, 2023). This success is, however, not alienated but is due to the continuous advancement in the model design architecture, training methods, and the extensive volume of textual corpora used for a broad spectrum of natural language processing (NLP) (Winiarski et al., 2020; OpenAI, 2023; Wang et al., 2023). LLMs can perform various NLP tasks,

such as machine translation, speech transcription (Bain et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2023), text generation, sentiment analysis, and question-answering (Mohapatra and Mohapatra, 2022).

However, through recent studies, GPTs are currently being explored in robotic tasks and applications such as embodied AI agents, reasoning, manipulation, and aerial navigation, among others (Wu et al., 2023; Vemprala et al., 2023) using natural language multimodal prompts and instructions as input (Vemprala et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2023) and automatically output actions containing the movement and position transitions in a progressive level of reasoning (Ren et al., 2023) or generate a code-base task and platforms as modules that get the robot to act accordingly on deployment, removing the service of prompt engineers from the current robotic pipeline or loop according to Vemprala et al. (2023). Wake et al. (2023) developed a highly responsive chatbot based on GPT that integrated with a co-speech visual gesture generation system that selected appropriate gestures based on the conceptual meaning of the speech. The emergence of GPT-3 and GPT-4 has led to a reimagining of the possibilities of artificial intelligence in a general context.

2.2. Socially Assistive Robotic Interventions in Healthcare

Socially assistive robotic interventions (SARI) in healthcare have emerged as a transformative approach, utilising the robustness of robotics to offer valuable support and interventions, particularly in child healthcare contexts. This novel paradigm addresses a range of conditions, including ASD (Lee et al., 2012), ADHD, NVLD, and social communication disorder SCD. The integration of socially assistive robotics (SAR) has yielded profound effects, reshaping perception, social behaviours, and emotional responses while providing structured interactions for individuals (Clabaugh et al., 2018; Chita-Tegmark and Scheutz, 2020).

Jain et al. (2020) contributed to the advancement of SARI by investigating user engagement in long-term, in-home interventions for children with autism. Employing supervised machine-learning algorithms, the study introduced both generalised and individualised engagement models, achieving remarkable accuracy levels of around 90% in post-hoc engagement classification. Notably, this success was evident despite the considerable variability present across users, sessions, and engagement states. The work sheds light on the potential to discern and respond to user disengagement in real-world human-robot interactions which underscored the feasibility and challenges of extended engagement monitoring.

Furthering the application of SARI in addressing the unique needs of children with ASD, Krithiga (2019) presented an innovative robotic solution. This child-friendly penguin-shape robot employed speech training and motion stabilisation techniques guided by personalised machine learning algorithms. The robot offered tailored support to children with varying degrees of ASD-related challenges by facilitating daily training sessions under supervision. This design exemplified the

potential of SAR to provide individualised, consistent assistance, potentially transforming the way children with ASD receive interventions.

In the pursuit of enhancing therapeutic activities through SARI, Katsanis and Moulianitis (2020) delved into the world of SAR interventions for children with ASD. Their comprehensive review of recent literature highlights diverse robot designs and their roles in assisting children with autism. Introducing a set of application and design criteria, the authors assess the effectiveness of seven robots using a grading system. This systematic evaluation underscores the growing interest and potential of SAR in supporting and engaging children with autism, reflecting the field's dedication to exploring innovative ways of improving the lives of those affected.

In unison, these papers illuminated the progressive integration of SARI into child healthcare, particularly in addressing autism spectrum disorder (Tamantini et al., 2021; Kouroupa et al., 2022). Through the development of advanced engagement recognition models, personalised robotic solutions, and systematic assessments of SAR effectiveness, researchers are forging a path towards more meaningful and impactful interventions for children with various developmental challenges. As technology continues to evolve, the potential for SAR to revolutionise healthcare interventions remains promising and inspiring.

2.2.1. Robotic Assistive Diagnostic Interventions

A look at the collection of research today on robotic assistive diagnostic interventions (RADI) reveals that this area of study has gained significant attention. In healthcare, RADIs are innovative tools for addressing diagnostic challenges (Jain et al., 2020; Macdonald et al., 2021). However, The development of numerous robotic systems to assist the elderly in everyday tasks, keep track of their health, and give companionship is shown by a survey of some of the most significant research (Coşar et al., 2020; Romero-Garcés et al., 2022). Systems like these can help with movement, warn caregivers of crises, and even remind patients to take their prescriptions (Jain et al., 2020; Macdonald et al., 2021; Coşar et al., 2020; Romero-Garcés et al., 2022).

2.2.2. Robotic Assistive Therapeutic Interventions

Robotic assistive therapeutic interventions (RATI) have gained prominence as a dynamic approach to addressing the complex challenges of autism spectrum disorder (ASD), offering multifaceted methods that encompass conversation-based, game-based, and entertainment-based strategies (Rakhymbayeva, Amirova, and Sandygulova, 2021). These interventions systematically analyse the child's behaviour, engagement levels, and eye observations, ultimately contributing to their overall well-being.

Lee et al. (2012) contributed to this evolving landscape. They examined the influence of specific robot features on children with ASD. Their study highlighted the impact of a robot's appearance, revealing

that a toy-like face and limb movement capability enhance children's attention and facial expression abilities. This insight underscored the potential for robots to effectively engage and positively influence autistic children's social interactions. Srinivasan et al. (2015) delved deeper into robot-assisted therapy, conducting an 8-week study involving 36 children diagnosed with ASD. Through distinct sessions, the study investigated the effects of rhythmic interactions and robotic assistance on positive, negative, and stereotyped behaviours. Encouragingly, the rhythm group and the robotic assistance group demonstrated increase positive affect, with the rhythm group also showcased a reduction in negative behaviours. These findings emphasised the promising potential of robot-assisted interventions in modulating emotional and behavioural responses in autistic children.

A tailored approach to robot-assisted interventions is illuminated by Rakhymbayeva, Amirova, and Sandygulova (2021), who introduce individualized therapy by programming robots to adapt to different forms of autism. This personalised intervention is designed to engage each child based on their specific condition, with familiar activities fostering higher engagement and unfamiliar ones evoking differing responses. Such adaptive strategies underscored the significance of customization in optimising the effectiveness of robot-assisted therapeutic interactions. This evolution towards utilising robots as assistive technology in therapy has led to the emergence of a burgeoning field. Ackovska et al. (2017) showcased the integration of the NAO humanoid robot in research experiments involving children with ASD, illustrating the growing trend of incorporating humanoid robots as valuable tools in rehabilitative contexts.

In summary, significant progress had been made in recent years in realizing the potential of robot-assisted treatment, particularly for ASD youngsters (Ackovska et al., 2017; Bharatharaj et al., 2017; Billing et al., 2020). Combining cutting-edge functions, individualized strategies, and thorough behavioural assessments, robots have the potential to revolutionize therapeutic treatments and open new opportunities for improving the lives of people with autism (Baraka et al., 2022).

2.2.3. Robotic Assistive Interactive Interventions

Robotic assistive interactive interventions (RAII) have emerged as a multifaceted approach aimed at fostering fundamental communication skills in children, particularly those with social skill difficulties like autism spectrum disorder (ASD). These interventions encompass both verbal and non-verbal communication strategies, each contributing uniquely to children's social communication development.

Non-verbal communication is a pivotal aspect of RAI, as highlighted by Rakhymbayeva, Amirova, and Sandygulova (2021). Their study offered insights into non-verbal elements such as facial expressions and gestures, shedding light on their significance in facilitating effective communication between children and robots. Also, the role of verbal interactions in RAI gained prominence through research (Lee et al., 2012; Boccia et al., 2016; and Bharatharaj et al., 2017). These studies

underscored how children, especially those with ASD, exhibit a preference for verbal interaction with robots over human therapeutic agents. Incorporating advanced features like facial expressions and gestures into robots enhanced interaction quality and contributes to the development of broader social communication skills.

The transformative potential of RAI in healthcare is exemplified by Romero-Garcés et al. (2022). Their work outlined the evolution of the CLARA robot, highlighting the dynamic shift from technical feasibility to user-centred co-creative approaches. They showcased the significant strides made in designing SARs to support independent living and reduced the burden on carers. Building on this, Chita-Tegmark and Scheutz (2020) emphasised SARs' role in enhancing social well-being by mediating interactions and positively influencing individuals with health conditions. Their proposed framework of social mediation functions aligns with the unique needs of individuals, paving the way for SARs to play a pivotal role in fostering social engagement.

Further expanding the scope of RAI, Esfandbod et al. (2022) introduced a socially assistive robot, RASA, in speech therapy for children with language disorders. The study showcased the robot's potential to enhance engagement and effectiveness in speech therapy sessions, offered a promising avenue for improving language skills in children. Within the sphere of older adults, Tobis et al. (2022) highlighted the impact of interaction with autonomous social robots on perceptions of technology in elder care. This study underscored the importance of pre-implementation interactions to facilitate users' understanding and adaptability to robotic interventions.

Finally, Macdonald et al. (2021) undertook a scoping review to explore assistive technologies beyond robots that support social interaction in long-term care settings (Macdonald et al., 2022). Their comprehensive approach seeks to address the loneliness and isolation prevalent in such environments, providing valuable insights for practise and policy.

Collectively, these literatures showcased the diverse facets of RAI, ranging from non-verbal communication and safety considerations to interactive engagement, mediating social interactions, enhancing speech therapy, and addressing the needs of older adults. These advancements contribute to a holistic framework for fostering communication skills and social engagement, particularly in populations with unique challenges.

2.3. Assessment of Social Robot Engagements

Assessing the engagement level of social robots is critical in understanding the effectiveness of the interventions provided by the social robots. A series of innovative approaches and insights across multiple research endeavours. Billing et al. (2020) kick-started this exploration by presenting a comprehensive dataset designed for evaluating robot-enhanced therapy (RET). This extensive compilation encapsulates over 3000 therapeutic sessions spanning more than 300 hours, involving

61 children with ASD. The sessions, encompassing interactions with both the social robot NAO and therapists, adhered to the applied behaviour analysis (ABA) protocol. This meticulous recording utilised multiple cameras to capture intricate details of children's behaviour, yielding a rich 3D dataset encompassing eye gaze, head position, body motion, orientation, and metadata variables such as age, gender, and autism diagnosis.

Central to the enhancement of autism therapy is the concept of engagement measurement, explored by Rakhymbayeva et al. (2022). This study delved into a data-driven approach, investigating the transferability of an engagement model across different datasets. By employing publicly available datasets, PInSoRo and Qamqor, the authors evaluated the model's accuracy in transferring knowledge. Their exploration of transfer learning methodology demonstrated its potential to enhance accuracy in engagement model transference between datasets thereby shedding light on the importance of data congruence for effective model application.

The pursuit of advancing robot-assisted therapy (RAT) into the realm of robotic enhanced therapy (RET) is captured by Cao et al. (2019). Their overview of the "DREAM" project highlighted the collaborative efforts of interdisciplinary experts, including roboticists, ethicists, cognitive scientists, computer scientists, and psychotherapists. This collective endeavour led to the development of a supervised autonomous robotic system surpassing traditional remote-control methods, with an emphasis on safe and ethical robot behaviour. The project's promising clinical studies showcased comparable performance between RET and human standard therapy, setting the stage for further advancements in assisting children with ASD.

Salhi et al. (2022) contributed to this narrative by exploring the integration of humanoid social robots into paediatric hospital care units. Employing deep learning and reinforcement learning algorithms, their study aimed to create consistent therapeutic experiences for children with communication capacity restrictions. This research showcased the development of a humanoid robot, NAO, with capabilities ranging from detecting autism using convolutional neural networks to recommending and executing therapy-based tasks which promised to elevate the therapeutic outcomes for children in need of specialised care.

Moreover, Alabdulkareem, Alhakbani, and Al-Nafjan (2022) emphasised the potential for interactive and engaging sessions within RAIL. This interactivity served as a platform for children to practise complex forms of human interaction, potentially leading to more profound skill acquisition. In the broader context, the growing interest in interactive robots for children with ASD is highlighted by Alabdulkareem, Alhakbani, and Al-Nafjan (2022). Recent studies underscore the potential of interactive robots to capture the interest and engagement of children with autism, offering a compelling avenue for exploration and innovation.

Collectively, these studies coalesce around the common theme of leveraging social robots to enhance autism therapy, offering comprehensive datasets, engagement assessment methodologies, autonomous robotic systems, and innovative humanoid interventions. Through these diverse perspectives, researchers are unravelling the potential of robotic interventions to transform the therapeutic landscape for children with autism spectrum disorder.

2.4. Safety Concerns with Robotic Assisted Interventions

The integration of safety measures enhances the overall effectiveness and reliability of RAIL. Safety remains a paramount consideration in human-robot collaboration (Liu et al., 2020). In the study, Liu et al. (2020) presented a novel real-time collision avoidance approach for a mobile manipulator, combining safety considerations with efficiency to enable safe interaction between humans and robots in collaborative environments. Also, still addressing safety concerns, Katsanis and Moulianitis (2021) proposed an architecture that models and categorises interactions in autism interventions. This innovative approach ensured safe child-robot interactions by detecting potential distractions that may impact the child's well-being. Also, the DREAM project which highlighted the collaborative efforts of interdisciplinary experts in the development of a supervised autonomous robotic system surpassing traditional remote-control methods, still emphasised on safe and ethical behaviour for social robots (Cao et al., 2019).

3.0 System Requirement and Analysis

The establishment of comprehensive system requirements forms the cornerstone of the endeavour. In this chapter, the system requirements of the project will be outlined showing the detailed specifications and functionalities that the TIAGo robot, integrated with LLMs such as Whisper and GPT-3, needs to exhibit to effectively facilitate robot-assisted interventions for children with social skill difficulties. These integrations lead to the development of a chatting software deployed on the robot codenamed, *TIAGoGPT*.

These requirements serve as a comprehensive roadmap to guide the development, implementation, and evaluation of the system, ensuring that it meets the project's objectives and provides meaningful support to its target users. The system requirements establish a clear framework for the integration of LLMs into the robot's functionality. By outlining the specific capabilities, interactions, and technical aspects. This enables it to engage in natural language conversations, generate relevant responses, and foster social skill development in a controlled and supportive manner.

Figure 3.1: The Proposed TIAGoGPT System

3.1. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements

The system requirement involves identifying, documenting, and understanding the specific needs, functionalities, and constraints that the system must satisfy within the context of the project.

3.1.1. Functional Requirements

The functional requirements of this project form the core specifications that outline how the TIAGo robot will utilise LLMs, specifically Whisper and GPT-3, to provide effective support and intervention for children facing social skill difficulties. These requirements define the essential capabilities that the robot must possess to engage in meaningful conversations, understand user input, generate coherent responses, and create an interactive and supportive environment for the target users.

The integration of LLMs introduces transformative potential to the TIAGo robot, enabling it to bridge communication gaps, offer guidance, and foster social skill development in children. The functional requirements are carefully designed to harness the power of natural language processing while excluding non-verbal cues, gestures, and behavioural recognition, thus streamlining the focus on language-based interactions.

Key Components of Functional Requirements are as follows:

1. Initialisation and Testing

On initialising the TIAGoGPT (the project name to identify the developed software, also referred to as system), the system should confirm availability and accessibility to the robot's I/O devices specifically, the microphone and speakers and proceed to the home page. On a contrary note, the system should report the error and terminates.

2. Consent Request

The TIAGoGPT should display a consent form with check boxes, input field, and buttons for the user to accept or decline. User will have to select the check box, type in full name in the name field, and click on the accept button to provide consent after reading through the consent request details. To decline consent, user only need to click on the decline button.

Only the selected options should be activated upon acceptance. For example, if the user provide consent, then the option for 'text' and 'voice' interaction mode will be available for the user, however, if the user decline consent, only the 'text' mode will be available. The user should be able to identify if the consent is on behalf of a minor who he/ she is the legal guardian.

3. User Interaction

The user who provided consent should be able to choose interaction mode preferred interaction mode - 'text' or 'voice' which opens the control for the chosen mode on the default tab. The user should be able to switch interaction modes by adding additional tabs or using previously open tabs. Adding additional tab is by clicking the add icon or 'CTRL + T' on the keyboard as shortcut.

On entering the interaction mode, TIAGoGPT should start the conversation with the initial prompt: “Hello ‘user first name’, and welcome!” or “Hello, and welcome!” (in the case of a declined consent user).

The user should continue the conversation by clicking ‘start voice’ to start interacting with the TIAGo robot via the TIAGoGPT interface in voice mode or type the text prompt in the message field and click the ‘submit text’ button to submit the prompt for response from TIAGo robot.

For a voice mode interaction, the user should be able to send other prompts once the TIAGo robot finishes responding to each prompt continuously, but the user will have to type and click on the ‘submit text’ button for each prompt sent in a text mode.

The user should be able to close any tab by clicking on the close (‘x’) icon located on the affected tab.

4. Voice Input Processing

The TIAGoGPT should convert the voice input prompt received from the microphone to electrical signals and then to a digital format through the robot device middleware.

5. Speech Transcription

The TIAGoGPT should produce a readable text format transcription of the digital format of the initial voice prompt using the Whisper model taking a batch prompt of 20 seconds.

6. Text Response Generation

The TIAGoGPT should generate a related response using the GPT-3.5-turbo model based on the voice transcription.

7. Text Synthesis

The TIAGoGPT should synthesize the generated response using the Google Text-to-Speech model.

8. Output Generation

The TIAGoGPT should display produce both the synthesised sound and the generated text response through its output devices, such as speakers and the graphical user interface (GUI).

9. Data Storage

The TIAGoGPT should store copies of voice prompts and synthesized responses in the repository while the user has the menu to save their conversation to either the database or as file in the system repository.

10. End Conversation

The TIAGoGPT should ends the conversation and returns to the home page once the user sends ‘Goodbye’ or “I’m done for now” prompt. This shows the end of conversation with that

user. The TIAGoGPT should return to the home page ready for another user. The user can equally click on the Exit in the File menu list.

Table 3.1: *Functional Requirements and Their Priority Levels*

S/No	Functional Requirement	Priority Level
1	Initialisation and Testing	Low
2	Consent Request	High
3	User Interaction	Medium
4	Voice Input Processing	High
5	Speech Transcription	High
6	Response Generation	High
7	Text Synthesis	High
8	Output Generation	High
9	Data Storage	High
10	End Conversation	Medium

3.1.2. Non-Functional Requirements

In addition to the functional capabilities that drive the core interactions of the TIAGo robot using Large Language Models (LLMs), a set of non-functional requirements is crucial to ensuring the overall effectiveness, usability, and ethical considerations of the robot-assisted interventions. These non-functional requirements focus on aspects beyond pure functionality, encompassing qualities that contribute to the success and safety of the system.

By addressing non-functional requirements, we aim to create a well-rounded and reliable system that not only communicates effectively but also upholds the highest standards of security, performance, and user experience. These requirements ensure that the integration of LLMs into the TIAGo robot aligns with the project's ethical principles and provides a seamless and safe experience for children with social skill difficulties and their caregivers.

Key Components of Non-Functional Requirements:

1. Integration

The TIAGoGPT pretrained models for voice transcription (Whisper), response generation (GPT-3.5-turbo), and speech synthesis (Google cloud Text-to-Speech) should seamlessly be integrated.

2. Performance

The TIAGoGPT should have high performance leading to low latency in voice processing, transcription, and response generation to ensure real-time interaction with users.

3. Reliability

The TIAGoGPT should be highly reliable in responding, ensuring that its core functions are consistent without frequent failures or disruptions. The voice recording should be greatly relied on to capture the user's speech effectively.

4. Security

The TIAGoGPT should ensure the confidentiality and integrity of user data, including voice prompts and generated responses. The user should also feel safe using the system.

5. Scalability

The TIAGoGPT should be able to handle large amounts of voice data storage efficiently and reliably.

6. Usability

The TIAGoGPT interfaces should be user-friendly with clear instructions for interaction. The system should provide appropriate feedback or indications to users during different stages of the interaction and with status messages to encourage usage by the user.

7. Maintainability

The TIAGoGPT should be designed in a modular and extensible manner to facilitate future updates and bug fixes. The maintainability of TIAGoGPT will have a low priority level.

8. Quality

The TIAGoGPT should undergo thorough testing and validation to ensure accuracy and compliance with requirements.

9. Suitability

The TIAGoGPT should provide relevant responses to user prompts; however, less attention is paid on this regard.

Table 3.2: *Non-Functional Requirements and Their Priority Levels*

S/No	Non-Functional Requirement	Priority Level
1	Integration	High
2	Performance	High
3	Reliability	High
4	Security	High
5	Scalability	Low
6	Usability	High
7	Maintainability	Medium
8	Quality	High
9	Suitability	High

3.2. Software Requirement

The success of the project's TIAGoGPT chat software hinges on a clear understanding of its functional and non-functional needs. In this project, the software requirements serve as a foundational framework that establishes a comprehensive overview of the technical aspects that will guide the development efforts. It encompasses a range of vital elements, including the programming language and framework, libraries, development environment, system prerequisites, and interaction with external resources such as the OpenAI API. This section outlines the essential software components, tools, and dependencies that will be employed to bring the envisioned solution to fruition.

3.2.1. Platforms and Frameworks

The TIAGoGPT software is developed using the Python programming language and the PyQt framework, which helped to create cross-platform applications and provided the software with a graphical user interface (GUI). In essence, this shows that the program is cross-platform compatible, having been created on a Windows computer before being made available on the Ubuntu LTS Linux version which is the deployment Window of TIAGo lite robot. The TIAGoGPT requires a minimum of Python 3.9 or higher, the PyQt 6 LTS framework, Windows 10 or higher, and Ubuntu 20.04 LTS or higher. However, it is highly recommended to use Ubuntu 22.10 LTS or newer, as the previous version will stop receiving updates by April 2025.

3.2.2. Development Environment

Visual Studio Code (VS Code) serves as the primary integrated development environment (IDE) employed for efficient organisation of various aspects of the software's development. It acted as a central hub for managing essential components such as application directory structure, resources, and the intricate structure of Python and other codebase files. It facilitated seamless code writing, editing, and organisation, enhancing overall productivity during the software development process. On the other hand, the use of a Python virtual environment was adopted, which helped in effective management of dependencies, ensuring that the TIAGoGPT relies on specific versions of libraries, packages, and modules that are vital for its functionality. It also helped in averting potential conflicts with other projects or system-wide dependencies by isolating these specific dependencies within the virtual environment.

3.2.3. Dependencies and Libraries

The successful integration and operation of the TIAGoGPT software rely on several key libraries, dependencies, and APIs, each playing a specific role in achieving the desired functionality and user experience. This integration involved the OpenAI API, Google Cloud API, PyQt 6 LTS libraries, PyAudio, Pygame, Requests, JSON, and potentially other relevant libraries. Together, these components enable the software to seamlessly interact with advanced language models, provide an

intuitive user interface, and manage data communication, thereby delivering a sophisticated and user-centric robot-assisted intervention platform.

3.2.4. Communication and API Access

Here, key prerequisites and configurations are needed. A stable internet connection is essential for accessing external services, including language processing and text-to-speech functions. Equally important for secure integration and authentication are valid API keys for accessing the Whisper, GPT-3 models, and Google Cloud TTS. Proper API endpoints are established for communication with OpenAI and Google Cloud TTS, enabling seamless data transmission. Secure authentication methods, like API keys, guarantee legitimate and secure interactions. Collectively, these measures create a robust foundation for the TIAGoGPT's interaction with external services, enhancing its capacity to provide meaningful interventions for children with social skill difficulties.

3.2.5. Documentation

The TIAGoGPT provides a detailed usage guidance, encompassing setup, operation, and problem-solving. It features clear and thorough comments and documentation throughout the codebase, elucidating the purpose and functionality of functions, classes, and methods. This ensures user-friendly navigation and facilitates understanding of the software's intricacies.

3.3. Hardware Requirements

In the pursuit of this project objectives, a solid foundation of hardware components forms the backbone of its success. These hardware requirements outline the essential components necessary to create a cohesive and effective environment where software, robotics, and human interaction converge seamlessly. It encompasses the robot's physical capabilities and the computational prowess of the host computer, the audio input and output devices, and optional components. Each component plays a crucial role in shaping the user experience and the efficacy of interventions. A careful selection and configuration of hardware components are pivotal in ensuring that all these are achieved. The following considerations were made as a minimum requirement to ensure optimal functionality and performance of the project (Build your own TIAGo, n.d.):

3.3.1. The TIAGo Robot Platform

The hardware for robot-assisted interventions is the TIAGo robot, which requires sensors, actuators, and processing for seamless integration. The robot platform used in this project is the TIAGo Lite version from Pal-Robotics. It is equipped with sensors such as a force-torque sensor on the wrist, customizable laser and sonar sensors, an inertial measurement unit (IMU), an RGB-D camera, two microphone arrays, and a touchscreen. There are also devices such as speakers, microphones, a display unit, and a power supply unit.

3.3.2. Computer System

A dedicated computer system for the development of the software application, which is to manage interactions between robot, user, and software, is required. However, the robot platform is embodied in a system unit capable of having similar requirements as the development computer system. The hardware should possess ample processing capacity and a good storage location. The minimum requirements are an 8GB of RAM (which is the amount of random-access memory that should be available to run the programme), an Intel i5 CPU, and at least a 250GB storage location available on the drive (either HDD or SSD).

3.3.3. Audio System

As part of the hardware requirement gathering, a high-quality microphone is essential for accurately capturing users' voices as audio input, and a reliable speaker system is necessary to facilitate the robot's speech output during interactions for effective communication with users. While a clear and precise audio input is crucial for the effectiveness of natural language understanding and generation, natural speech output is also important as it enhances the user experience during interactions. The deployment platform is equipped with $2 \times 5\text{ W}$ audio speakers and a $2 \times$ microphone array with stereo output between 50 and 8000 Hz. However, different specifications were used during the development phase of the project.

3.3.4. User Interactive Interface

Based on the project design, user interface devices such as touchscreens, buttons, or display units (a screen or LED panel) with a mouse and keyboard should be incorporated into the robot platform for taking input commands and outputting visual information to and from the user. It should meet the general specifications of such devices. Importantly, the robot platform has the basic user-interactive interface, which is the touchscreen. And apart from the software application being developed, the TIAGo robot also has a web-based user interface for a test function such as the software, actuators, and sensors diagnostics, text-to-speech triggers, pre-recorded motions, and demonstration executions. So, full control of the robot can be performed using the platform's interface.

3.3.5. Network Connectivity

The robot platform is equipped with wireless connectivity of 802.11ax Wi-Fi 6 and Bluetooth 4.0 and two GbE (Gigabit Ethernet) Ethernet ports. Stable and high-speed internet connectivity is crucial for accessing external resources, such as the OpenAI API and Google Cloud TTS API, and for facilitating real-time communication between the software application and external servers.

3.3.6. Power Supply

A standby 36V, 20 Ah battery with autonomy between 4 and 5 hours and a 12V, 5A power supply unit are equipped with the TIAGo robot platform to ensure a consistent power supply essential to prevent interruptions during software deployment, interactions, and data processing stages.

3.3.7. Extensible Supports

These are other necessary hardware component that will ease the development and deployment of the TIAGoGPT software system as expected. These components include laptop tray and mobile base mounting points, one USB 3.0, one USB 2.0, HDMI, and NVIDIA® Jetson™ TX2 Add-on.

4.0 System Design and Implementation

After putting together, the requirements needed for the development of the TIAGoGPT, breaking down the requirements into functional and non-functional, and even extending to establishing the hardware and software resources, it is important at this stage to begin writing the business logics for the software and assembling them together. In this chapter, the intricacies of the architectural blueprint that underpins the entire system are delved into. Firstly, it illuminates the technical details of how LLMs are seamlessly integrated into the TIAGo framework, enabling real-time language understanding and generation. Additionally, the design and development of a user-friendly software called TIAGoGPT, through which children engage with the robot, are showcased. This interface serves as a conduit for capturing speech patterns, which can be analysed further to enhance the efficacy of the intervention.

4.1. TIAGoGPT System Architecture

The proposed system architecture for the TIAGoGPT follows the model-view-controller (MVC) framework which encapsulates a harmonious fusion of multiple layers, each orchestrated to serve a crucial role in the interaction process as shown in Figure 4.1. At its core, the architecture capitalises on the cognitive prowess of LLMs, enabling the TIAGo robot to interpret, respond to, and facilitate meaningful dialogues with children. The focus lies in architecting a simple framework that seamlessly combines human-like linguistic understanding with personalised robotic interactions to foster social growth and skill development.

Figure 4.1: MVC Framework

Figure 4.2 below shows the model-view (MV) sections represented by these multilayers. The dynamic User Input Layer (UIL) is the anchor foundation where intuitive interfaces capture users input either as spoken language or typed text, fostering a natural and engaging interaction

environment. The user voice input of this layer is implemented in the Python file called *AudioRecordingModule*.

Figure 4.2: Proposed Architecture of TIAGoGPT System

Beneath the UIL lies the Speech Processing Layer (SPL) which integrates the speech transcription language model to identify and decode spoken language with appropriate representation in a textual readable format. To deepen engagement, the Language and Cognitive Processing Layer (LCPL) harnesses NLP by integrating GPT-3.5-turbo LLM to analysis and decode input language nuances and ensure contextually appropriate responses. This synthesis of input channels culminates in the Tonal Language Processing Layer (TLPL), where the TIAGoGPT infers pitch characteristics adjustment, enabling the robot to provide tailored, contextual, and sustainable interactions. These 3 layers are implemented in the *EndPointModule.py* file.

TIAGoGPTAppLauncher.py captures the fifth layer, the Robot Output Layer (ROL) which implements the TIAGo robot's speech response and the View component of the framework. All these orchestrated layers converge at this layer, echoing sounds in harmony with the generated response displayed. As the interaction unfolds, data is collected and stored for onward analysis within the Data Storage and Analysis Layer (DSAL) to drive continuous improvement and provide insights into the effectiveness of the interventions. This is the last layer implemented in the *DataStorageModule.py*.

4.2. TIAGoGPT Implementation

The implementation of TIAGoGPT, as depicted in Figure 4.3 below, represents a comprehensive and innovative system designed to facilitate robot-assisted interventions for children with social skill

difficulties. Here, the various stages of the implementation process are outlined. Consequently, careful attention has been paid to user consent, secure data storage, access control, and the incorporation of various AI models to offer effective voice transcription and response generation. The system's architecture, integration of essential components, and deployment process (as discussed in the subsequent chapter) have been meticulously designed to provide a holistic solution for supporting children with social skill difficulties.

Figure 4.3: Proposed Flowchart of TIAGoGPT System Implementation

4.2.1. Consent Module

The consent module is a pivotal component of the TIAGoGPT design and implementation, ensuring that legal, social, ethical, and professional considerations are upheld throughout the interactions between the TIAGo robot, LLMs, and the children participating in robot-assisted interventions which is in line with the project objectives. This module is designed to obtain explicit consent from carers, legal guardians, and relevant authorities, safeguarding the privacy, data usage, and rights of all involved parties. It comprises of 3 major components as discussed below which are: data usage and processing consent, third-party disclaimer, and opt-in and opt-out mechanism. Figure 4.4 shows the consent and disclaimer module as implemented.

Consent to Collect Data - Text and Voice Prompts

Dear user,

Introduction

This system, TIAGoGPT you are about to use is an MSc research project on "Exploring the Potentials of LLMs in TIAGo Robot-Assisted Interventions to Support Children with Social Skill Difficulties". The project implements cutting-edge technologies to revolutionise the field of child support. We employed state-of-the-art large language models in robotic assistive interventions for children with social skill difficulties. This means that the project system is deployed on a robot, and as part of our research study, children are expected to interact with the robot to enable us to reimagine the potential of this robot.

Mode

In line with our testing procedures, we want participants (from different backgrounds) to engage with the TIAGoGPT in at least a 10-minute conversation by asking the robot different questions exploratively while the system provides possible answers.

Consent Request

In light of the above, We write requesting your consent to collect and use data, including text and voice prompts, as part of our research study. Your participation and feedback are crucial as your responses will contribute to an academic research study exploring the potential of LLMs in TIAGo Robot-Assisted Interventions (RAI) for supporting children with social skill difficulties.

What Data Will Be Collected

1. Text Prompts: We may collect data in the form of text responses provided by you through the Tiago Robot - 'TIAGoGPT' software. These responses will be used for

I hereby give my consent for the collection and use of my data as described above.

Legal guardian providing consent on behalf of a minor? (if yes, please select)

I hereby with hold my consent

Figure 4.4: Consent and Disclaimer Module Implementation

1. Data Usage and Processing Consent

This section provides information on how users data are used, processed, stored, and managed. It also specifies the deletion period. This detailed the critical importance of obtaining explicit permission from users before collecting, processing, and utilizing their data within the TIAGoGPT system. This consent serves as a foundational aspect of ethical AI implementation, ensuring transparency, user empowerment, and compliance with privacy regulations. The system establishes a framework of trust and accountability, assuring users that their data will be handled responsibly and aligned with their preferences.

2. Third-Party Disclaimer

The disclaimer serves as a statement acknowledging and informing users about the involvement of external images (e.g., the TIAGo Robot), services, APIs, or technologies in the TIAGoGPT system. This disclaimer highlights that certain functionality, such as voice transcription, may rely on third-party services. Users are made aware that their interactions might involve sharing data with these external entities, necessitating their understanding and acceptance of any terms and conditions associated with such services. This disclaimer ensures transparency and helps users make informed decisions regarding their engagement with the system.

3. Opt-In and Opt-Out Mechanism

This mechanism, represented by the "Agree" and "Decline" buttons, provides users with the ability to choose whether they want to participate in certain functionalities or data processing activities within the TIAGoGPT system (as described above). "Opt-In" or "Agree" refers to the action of willingly enabling a specific feature or allowing data processing, while "Opt-Out" or "Decline" involves the decision to disable or discontinue that feature or data processing. This mechanism respects users' preferences and privacy by giving them control over how their data is used and ensuring compliance with data protection regulations. It empowers users to customize their experience and enhances transparency in the system's data practices. Most importantly, when a user declines consent, it does not disapprove the user's ability to interact with the system but only limits those functionalities that require the system to store their data.

4.2.2. Audio Recording (AR) Module

The AR Module initiates the process by capturing audio inputs from the children. This involves the use of microphones and audio sensors equipped on the TIAGo robot, strategically positioned to capture the child's speech clearly. The *AudioRecorder()* module of the *TIAGoGPT* is set in recording mode as soon as the 'voice start' button is clicked by the user where the system keeps listening for audio signal that meets a certain criterion before start recording and, at the end of TIAGo audio response. The recording stops when the audio signal falls within the background noise or unwanted signals low level. To gain the desired result regardless of TIAGo microphone specification, the following considerations were made:


```

modules > AudioRecordingModule.py > ...
1 import pyaudio
2 import numpy as np
3 import soundfile as sf
4 import time, os
5 from controller.AppController import AudioManager
6
7 # User Voice Input Layer (UIL)
8 class AudioRecorder:
9     def __init__(self, duration=20, sample_rate=44100, channels=1, max_threshold=2000, min_threshold=20, silence_duration=1):
10         self.duration = duration
11         self.sample_rate = sample_rate
12         self.channels = channels
13         self.max_threshold = max_threshold
14         self.min_threshold = min_threshold
15         self.silence_duration = silence_duration
16
17         self.audio_manager = AudioManager()
18         # self.audio = pyaudio.PyAudio()
19         self.frames = []
20         self.stream = None
21         self.is_recording = False
22
23     def startRecording(self):
24         self.frames = []
25         silence_frames = []
26         self.is_recording = True
27         recording_started = False
28         silence_started = False
29         start_time = None

```

Figure 4.5: Audio Module Implementation

1. Sample Rate

Sample rate f_s determines how many times per second the analogue audio signal is measured and converted into a digital representation. In other words, it is the number of samples of audio carried per second, measured in Hertz (Hz) (Dunn, 2017). Being a frequency dependent variable, it can be expressed in terms of frequency as the frequency range that can accurately capture and represent the digital audio signal. For example, a sample rate of 44,100 Hz (i.e., 44,100 samples per second) can accurately represent audio frequencies with better output quality up to approximately 22,000 Hz, which covers the entire audible range for humans including children.

2. Maximum and Minimum Thresholds

The thresholds of the audio signal during recording are the reference points of the audio signal considered as significant or silence based on mainly the individual's vocal intensity. Maximum threshold A_{\max} is set to determine when speech starts by allowing the audio signal to pass through the gate only when the signal's amplitude exceeds a specified level while the minimum threshold A_{\min} is set to as one of the criteria to stop recording to suppress the background noise or unwanted low-level signals. In the context of this project, a maximum and minimum thresholds

3. Signal and Silence Durations

The signal duration T represents the length of the audio recording in seconds while the silence duration S is the duration of silence that is considered significant (not noise). The silence duration is used as a criterion for an audio signal to stop being recorded when the audio signal amplitude goes below the minimum threshold and continues for a period of S seconds within an instance. This is needed to ensure that silence period is not unnecessarily prolonged after recording had commenced. It is observed that in the midst of audio signals, there can be instances where the audio signal falls below the minimum threshold, however, it is expected that in an interaction, a longer silence period means an end to the prompt paving way for the response processing to commence.

The parameters used are as follows:

- Signal Duration, $T = 20$ seconds.
- Sample Rate, $f_s = 44100$ Hz (samples per second)
- Channels, $C = 1$ being the number of audio channels in the recording
- Max Threshold, $A_{\max} = 2000$ (amplitude units) being the maximum amplitude value above which sound is considered significant.
- Min Threshold, $A_{\min} = 20$ (amplitude units) being the minimum amplitude value below which sound is considered silence.

- Silence Duration, $S = 1$ sec, being the length of time that the signal has no sound or very low amplitude.
- Frame per buffer, $F = 1024$, being the number of audio samples that are processed in one chunk of data.

Given these parameters, we can derive some relationships mathematically (Don and Davis, 2008):

Total Number of Samples N : The total number of samples in the recording is the product of the sample rate and the duration.

$$N = T \times f_s$$

Equation 1

Total Number of Channels: This is the number of samples multiplied by the number of channels.

i.e.,

$$C \geq 1$$

Amplitude Range, A : The difference between the maximum threshold and minimum threshold represents the range of amplitudes considered for sound.

$$A = A_{\max} - A_{\min}$$

Equation 2

Amplitude Range per Sample, a : The amplitude range per sample is the amplitude range divided by the total number of samples.

$$a = \frac{A}{N}$$

Equation 3

For the silence duration denoted by

$$S = N_s \times t_s$$

Equation 4

, where N_s is the number of silent samples, and t_s is the sampling interval.

These relationships provide a deeper understanding of how different factors interact and affect the quality, accuracy, and efficiency of audio recording and processing. While many audio parameter values are often determined empirically as in this context or based on industry standards, understanding their mathematical relationships helped in enhancing the

signal-to-noise ratio, audio quality, allocating optimal resource, and ultimately ensuring accurate speech recognition, avoiding information loss due to inadequate sampling during the and transcription process.

4.2.3. Whisper Model Integration

The Whisper model from OpenAI is a multilingual automatic speech recognition (ASR) system with a multi-task capability including language identification, speech transcription, among others (Bain et al., 2023). It is integrated and accessed through its API. The API is an endpoint that connect the audio recording module to the Whisper model *whisper – 1* to converts the spoken words of the children captured by the AR module and stored in the repository as *media file*, into textual form as the *response_format*. The whisper transcription model method *Audio.transcribe()* takes 4 arguments: *api_key*, *model*, *file*, and *response_format*. However, it is important to note that the language identification which is the task of detecting the language of a spoken utterance precedes the transcription. This module employs advanced ASR techniques to accurately transcribe the verbal inputs. The transcribed text is then passed to the dialogue management engine for further processing.

```

14 # Speech Processing Layer (SPL)
15 class Transcriber(EndPoint):
16     def __init__(self, api_key):
17         super().__init__(api_key)
18         self.openai = openai
19         self.api_key = api_key
20         self.model_id = 'whisper-1'
21
22     def transcribeVoice(self, prompt):
23         media_file_path = prompt
24         media_file = open(file=media_file_path, mode='rb')
25
26         response = self.openai.Audio.transcribe(
27             api_key=self.api_key,
28             model=self.model_id,
29             file=media_file,
30             response_format = 'text' # text, json, srt, vtt
31         )
32         print("Audio recording transcribed -----SUCCESS")
33         return response

```

Figure 4.6: Implementation of Transcription (*whisper*) Model Integration

4.2.4. Response Generation Module

The response generation module is made up of the *gpt – 3.5 – turbo* model and the *token*. The token acts as a filtration system for the model, helping to place some constraints on and tone the output generated by the model by providing additional context. The sections below provide a more detailed explanation.

1. GPT-3.5-turbo Model Integration

The GPT-3.5-turbo model integration is a pivotal component of the project which represents a groundbreaking leap in human-robot interaction, harnessing the immense linguistic

capabilities of the model to facilitate natural and engaging verbal interactions between the TIAGo robot and children with social skill difficulties. As children initiate conversations, the speech recognition subsystem comprising of the audio recorder and the transcription modules' captures spoken words as prompts and converts them into text in a voice mode interaction, which is then fed into the GPT-3.5-turbo model. The model is integrated through its API with *temperature*, *max_tokens*, and *message* argument of *ChatCompletion.create()* method set to 1.0, 100, and *prompt* from the transcription model respectively. The model has a returns type of dictionary containing *usage* and *content*.

```

79 # GPT-3.5-turbo response model
80 def generateResponse(self, prompt, max_tokens=100, temperature=1.0): # max_tokens reduced from 1000 to 100
81     try:
82         self.messages.append({'role': 'user', 'content': prompt})
83         response = self.openai.ChatCompletion.create(
84             model='gpt-3.5-turbo',
85             max_tokens=max_tokens,
86             temperature=temperature,
87             messages=self.messages
88         )
89         print("Response generated by TiagoGPT -----SUCCESS")
90         self.messages.append({'role': 'assistant', 'content': response.choices[0].message.content})
91         # self.text_synthesis.synthesizeText(response.choices[0].message.content)
92         return {'usage': response.usage.total_tokens, 'content': response.choices[0].message.content}
93     except Exception as e:
94         return {'error': e}
95

```

Figure 4.7: Implementation of GPT-3.5-turbo Model Integration

2. Special Tokens

Special tokens refer to specific tokens that have predefined meanings or functions within the model's architecture. These tokens serve various purposes and allow for the control or customisation of the model behaviour during text generation or processing. Special tokens are recognised by the model and trigger specific actions or behaviours. In this context, special tokens were used to set the system name as *TIAGoGPT*, response length, purpose, etc by providing in a message dictionary *system* as the role and clear and concise prompts that instruct the model on what is to be done as content as demonstrated in the code block below. These prompts are placed at the beginning of conversations. It is important to count the tokens in the customised input and the generated output and ensure they do not exceed the model's token limit which is usually 4096 tokens.

```

messages = [{"role": "system",
             "content": "You are a helpful assistant."}]

```

4.2.5. Google Cloud Text-to-Speech (TTS) Module

The Text-to-Speech (TTS) engine takes the textual responses from GPT-3.5-turbo and transforms them into natural and expressive speech. The TIAGo robot utters these responses, creating a seamless and engaging conversational experience for the children. The *client.synthesize_speech()* takes a *request* of type dictionary with values *input*, *voice*, and *audio_config*

```
def synthesizeText(self, text):
    """Synthesizes speech from the input string of text."""
    input_text = texttospeech.SynthesisInput(text=text)
    voice = texttospeech.VoiceSelectionParams(
        language_code="en-US",
        name="en-US-Standard-C",
        ssml_gender=texttospeech.SsmlVoiceGender.FEMALE,
    )
    audio_config = texttospeech.AudioConfig(
        audio_encoding=texttospeech.AudioEncoding.MP3
    )
    response = self.client.synthesize_speech(
        request={"input": input_text, "voice": voice, "audio_config": audio_config}
    )

    print("Generated response Synthesised -----SUCCESS")
    self.audio_manager.save_output(response.audio_content, filetype="output")
    # Play the recently saved audio content
    self.autoplay(self.audio_manager.recent_file_finder())
```

Figure 4.8: Google Cloud TTS Service Integration

4.2.6. Storage and File System

The storage system manages the storage of user interactions, utilising both a database for unstructured data and files for audio recordings and logs.

4.2.7. Multiprocessor – Thread Management

The multiprocessor efficiently manages threads, *QThread* object handling concurrent interactions such as voice recording, transcription, response generation, and user input processing without causing conflicts or bottlenecks, ensuring smooth and responsive user experiences. These complex operations are performed in the background without experiencing delays, freezes, or slowdowns in the system while users keep interacting with the application in real-time. This is implemented from the *PyQt6.QtCore*.

4.3. Additional Modules Implemented

Apart from the above-listed features, which form part of the implementation section, each module listed below contributes to the overall functionality and user experience of your project, ensuring seamless voice-based interactions, data security, and effective communication. Here are the functionalities summary:

1. Dual Conversation Mode Module - Text-based and Voice-based

This module offers the user the flexibility to interact with the robot using their preferred input method. The user can either select voice or text as mode of interaction.

Figure 4.9: Text- and Voice- Based Conversation Interface Implementation

2. Prompt/ Response Displaying and Sounding Module

This module displays the user prompts and the generated responses and plays synthesised speeches. While the user could select input method of their choice, the output methods are set on dual mode i.e., both voice and text.

3. Data Security Framework

This module implements security measures to protect user data, including file disguising/ hashing, encryption, and access controls.

Figure 4.10: Data Security Framework Implementation

4. File Access Control

This module enforces access controls policy on stored users' files to ensure that only authorised persons or processes can access them.

5. Audit Log

The log feature keeps a record of important application events, e.g., voice recording and storage events, providing an audit trail for system activities and user interactions. One of the key aspects of this log is its safeguard against any unauthorised or malicious tampering. To ensure the authenticity and integrity of the logged data, a robust hash technology is employed.

The hash values act as digital fingerprints, representing the specific content of each log entry. In the event of any alteration or tampering attempt, even a minor change in the log's content will lead to a significant alteration in the corresponding hash value.

6. Unit Testing Framework

This framework implements unit tests to verify the functionality of individual components and modules, ensuring code reliability.

7. Automatic Conversation Loop

The automatic conversation loop allows the TIAGoGPT to engage in continuous and dynamic conversations with users without interferences.

Figure 4.11: Automatic Conversation Loop Interface Implementation Shown

8. Personalised User Interaction

This feature tailors' interactions based on user preferences, history, and context, providing a personalised experience. The TIAGoGPT initiates conversation by calling the user by name at the introductory stage of the interaction.

4.4. Technology and Tools Used

The major technology used is the Qt framework.

4.4.1. Qt Framework

From Windows, macOS, and Linux to mobile platforms like Android and iOS, the Qt framework is a complete cross-platform development framework that enables the development of programs with a uniform user interface (UI) and functionality. Based on its cross-platform compatibility, code may be created once and deployed across several systems without requiring major changes.

A collection of tools and libraries called Qt are available for creating graphical user interfaces (GUIs). It contains a large variety of styleable and customizable UI components (widgets). Additionally, a signal and slot system are used for inter-object communication. This makes it easier to create dynamic and responsive apps (Jenn, 2023).

5.0 Testing and Deployment

The previous chapter anchored the TIAGoGPT design and development where various modules were implemented using the Qt framework. In this chapter, attention is focused on rigorously assessing the performance, effectiveness, and user experience of the developed TIAGoGPT through testing. Different testing methods were adopted ranging from the unit, non- and functional, and elaborate testing procedure. Moreso, the chapter also ended with the TIAGoGPT deployment demonstration.

5.1. TIAGoGPT System Testing

In the system testing, a broader view was taken to assess the functionalities of the TIAGoGPT software being developed. The essence was to analyse how different subsystems interact with each other after being integrated together. This testing method is essential as it could detect misalignment of dependencies and version incompatibility issues, which could have a varying effect on the entire system. Therefore, as noted, the testing was done with real-world dependencies to simulate the deployment environmental scenario. The diagram below (Figure 5.1) shows the various subsystems tested, with success as the test result.


```

(chat-with-robot) PS C:\Users\cmanj\OneDrive - University of Bradford\Documents\Project_Series\python_code\ai_systems\chat-with-robot> python app.py
pygame 2.5.0 (SDL 2.28.0, Python 3.11.2)
Hello from the pygame community. https://www.pygame.org/contribute.html
DB Connection Established -----SUCCESS
SqlDatabasePrivate::removeDatabase: connection 'qt_sql_default_connection' is still in use, all queries will cease to work.
SqlDatabasePrivate::addDatabase: duplicate connection name 'qt_sql_default_connection', old connection removed.
DB Connection Established -----SUCCESS
Consent saved at 1st location -----SUCCESS
Conversation started by TiagoGPT -----SUCCESS
Generated response Synthesised -----SUCCESS
Audio content written to file at C:\Users\cmanj\OneDrive - University of Bradford\Documents\Project_Series\python_code\ai_systems\chat-with-robot\media\audio\synthesized
/synthesized_audio_100823_135625.mp3
Listening...
Recording started!
Recording started at maximum threshold-----SUCCESS
Maximum recording duration reached...
Maximum recording duration reached.....SUCCESS
Recording completed.
Recorded audio saved as media/audio/recorded/recorded_audio_100823_135651.wav -----SUCCESS
Elapsed time: 10.052302598953247 seconds
Audio recording transcribed -----SUCCESS
Response generated by TiagoGPT -----SUCCESS
Generated response Synthesised -----SUCCESS
Audio content written to file at C:\Users\cmanj\OneDrive - University of Bradford\Documents\Project_Series\python_code\ai_systems\chat-with-robot\media\audio\synthesized
/synthesized_audio_100823_135656.mp3
Listening...
Recording started!
Recording started at maximum threshold-----SUCCESS
Maximum recording duration reached...
Maximum recording duration reached.....SUCCESS
Recording completed.
Recorded audio saved as media/audio/recorded/recorded_audio_100823_135724.wav -----SUCCESS
Elapsed time: 10.036249160766602 seconds
Audio recording transcribed -----SUCCESS
Response generated by TiagoGPT -----SUCCESS
Generated response Synthesised -----SUCCESS
Audio content written to file at C:\Users\cmanj\OneDrive - University of Bradford\Documents\Project_Series\python_code\ai_systems\chat-with-robot\media\audio\synthesized
/synthesized_audio_100823_135728.mp3
Listening...
Recording started!

```

Figure 5.1: TIAGoGPT System Testing

5.1.1. Unit Testing

There are about 8 functions, 52 methods, 16 objects, and 6 modules, used in the project. During the development phase of the TIAGoGPT, all the objects and their methods, modules, and other functions were individually tested in isolation to ensure that they worked as intended. At different point bugs were discovered and fixed before integrating them into the general system. This method

minimised complex issues propagation within the system due to failure of a unit. In Figure 5.1, the isolation of any subsystem tested as success or failure is the unit testing being performed.

5.1.2. Functional Testing

The functional testing which comprises of all the unit testing, current output, rating, and test outcomes are presented below:

Table 5.1: Functional Unit Testing and Results

SN	Functional Units	Current Output	Rating	Test Outcome
1	Initialisation and Testing (Components and dependencies initialisation)	TIAGoGPT loaded fully all dependencies on success and terminated on any failed attempt. Deletion of data stored that are more than the specified period.	High	SUCCESS
2	Consent Request (Accept or Decline consent)	Selectable options (accept and decline) and a name input field are displayed with consent well-worded in the text browser. Consent saved to databases.	High	SUCCESS
3	User Interaction (Initial and continuous interaction)	TIAGoGPT started the conversation by welcoming the user by name. The conversation continued with 'Listening' and 'Please wait' notice till the end. 2 modes: <i>Voice</i> and <i>Text</i>	High	SUCCESS
4	Voice Input Processing	Voice recording started only when the user started talking and ended 2 minutes after the user stopped.	High	SUCCESS
5	Speech Transcription	User speeches are transcribed by the <i>Whisper</i> model into text and processed.	High	SUCCESS
6	Response Generation	<i>GPT – 3.5 – turbo</i> generated text responses based on the user input.	High	SUCCESS
7	Text Synthesis	Google Cloud synthesised the generated text response using USA-standard English with a female voice.	High	SUCCESS
8	Output Generation	Generated text response displayed using <i>Qt TextBrowser</i> while also sounding the sound through the output device.	High	SUCCESS
9	Data Storage	Consent, audio, and chat history stored in the 3 different storage location. File access-controlled set on the folder.	High	SUCCESS
10	End Conversation	User ended conversation either by using the keyword " <i>goodbye</i> " or " <i>I'm done for now</i> ", or using the <i>Stop</i> button.	Medium	SUCCESS

5.1.3. Non-Functional Testing

The non-functional testing which comprises of all the appreciable elements, current output, rating, and test outcomes is presented below:

Table 5.2: *Non-Functional Elements Testing and Results*

S/N	Non-Functional Element	Current Output	Rating	Test Outcome
1	Integration	All models, components, and services integrated	High	SUCCESS
2	Performance	Latency in voice processing, transcription, and response generation	High	SUCCESS
3	Reliability	Consistent functions without disruption.	High	SUCCESS
4	Security	User consent and audit log data hashed and encrypted with access controls placed on the file system.	High	SUCCESS
5	Scalability	The system could handle large amount of voice data storage.	Low	SUCCESS
6	Usability	User-friendly system with clear instructions on usage	High	SUCCESS
7	Maintainability	Future updates and bug fixing in the TIAGoGPT are facilitated using modular method of coding.	Medium	SUCCESS
8	Quality	Accuracy and compliance with requirements ensured during testing.	High	SUCCESS
9	Suitability	Relevant responses to user prompt provided.	High	SUCCESS

5.1.4. Comprehensive Evaluation Testing

About 10 participants from different demography were invited to interact with the TIAGo robot, most specifically the TIAGoGPT, to access certain non-functional elements of the system. The usability of the robot interaction, effectiveness of the robot-assisted intervention (i.e., suitability), user interface and visuals, technical performance, as well as their experience and background with such a system, were measured using the participant feedback form. The participants were distributed as follows: 7 were adults, with 5 females and 2 males, while 3 children participated. Out of the 10 participants, only 8 completed the feedback form, and the summary of their responses to each component is as follows:

1. Usability Testing

The usability of the robot interaction was evaluated to determine how easily users could interact with the TIAGoGPT and perform tasks. Also, the user interface and visuals were

assessed for their design, layout, and visual elements for user friendliness. This is shown in Figure 5.2 – 5.4.

On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the ease of interacting with the TIAGo robot for the intended purpose? (1 = Very Difficult, 5 = Very Easy)

8 responses

Figure 5.2: Usability Testing Feedback Result from Users – (A)

Were the visuals engaging and suitable for the target audience (children with social skill difficulties)? (Yes/No)

8 responses

Figure 5.3: Usability Testing Feedback Result from Users - (B)

How would you rate the visual design and layout of the user interface? (1 = Very poor, 5 = Excellent)

8 responses

Figure 5.4: Usability Testing Feedback Result from Users - (C)

2. Effectiveness Testing

In Figure 5.5 below, the effectiveness of the robot-assisted intervention was measured by the impact and success of the robot's assistance in achieving its intended goals. From the result, all participants indicated the TIAGoGPT as helpful in the intervention drive.

Did you find the robot-assisted interventions helpful in supporting children with social skill difficulties? (Yes/No)
8 responses

Figure 5.5: Effectiveness Testing Feedback Result from Users

3. Technical Performance Testing

The TIAGoGPT's technical performance was assessed in terms of speed, accuracy, responsiveness, and reliability. In Figure 5.6, only 25% of the users experienced system glitches due to fluctuations in internet services while trying to interact with it.

Did you experience any technical issues or glitches during the interaction with the robot or the software? (Yes/No)
8 responses

Figure 5.6: Technical Performance Testing Feedback Result from Users

4. User Experience Testing

User experience and background were measured to understand how users with different backgrounds and experiences perceive and interact with the TIAGoGPT, considering factors like comfort, satisfaction, and engagement. As shown in Figure 5.7, an equal number of users had prior experience with robotic interventions.

Have you had any prior experience with robot-assisted interventions or similar technologies? (Yes/No)
8 responses

Figure 5.7: User Experience Testing Feedback Result from Users

5.2. TIAGoGPT Deployment

The TIAGoGPT deployment was done based on the software and hardware specifics as detailed in chapter 3. Aside from that, there were other deployment environment dependencies that could not be captured here but are all listed in the *Requirements.txt* file. Here are the steps followed in the successful deployment of TIAGoGPT onto TIAGo Robot:

Figure 5.8: TIAGoGPT Directory during Deployment

5.2.1. Creating a Python Virtual Environment

Linux system and Python *pip* were updated thereafter, a virtual environment with Python 3.10 or a later version was created to ensure a clean and isolated environment for your project. This was done by running the following Linux commands in the project folder:

```
sudo apt-get install -y update
sudo apt install python3-pip
python3 -m venv virt-env
```

5.2.2. Activating the Virtual Environment

The virtual environment was activated to work within its isolated environment. This step ensured that the required packages and dependencies are used in this environment rather than the system-wide Python installation. The activation is done using the command:

```
source virt-env/bin/activate
```

5.2.3. Installing PyAudio and PortAudio

The *sudo apt* package manager was used to install the *python3-pyaudio* and *portaudio19-dev* packages. This is required for *pyaudio wheel* to be built.

```
sudo apt-get install python3-pyaudio
sudo apt install portaudio19-dev
```

5.2.4. Installing the Required Dependencies

The *pip3* package manager was used to install the necessary dependencies listed in the *Requirements.txt* file. This file contained a list of required Python dependencies with their versions. Figure 5.9 below shows the names and versions of successfully installed packages.

```
pip3 install -r Requirements.txt
```



```

Successfully uninstalled PyTorch-6.5.2
Attempting uninstall: PyTorch-sip
Found existing installation: PyTorch-sip 13.5.2
Uninstalling PyTorch-sip-13.5.2:
Successfully uninstalled PyTorch-sip-13.5.2
Attempting uninstall: pygame
Found existing installation: pygame 2.5.1
Uninstalling pygame-2.5.1:
Successfully uninstalled pygame-2.5.1
Attempting uninstall: protobuf
Found existing installation: protobuf 4.24.0
Uninstalling protobuf-4.24.0:
Successfully uninstalled protobuf-4.24.0
Attempting uninstall: grpcio
Found existing installation: grpcio 1.57.0
Uninstalling grpcio-1.57.0:
Successfully uninstalled grpcio-1.57.0
Attempting uninstall: PyTorch
Found existing installation: PyTorch 6.5.2
Uninstalling PyTorch-6.5.2:
Successfully uninstalled PyTorch-6.5.2
Attempting uninstall: googleapis-common-protos
Found existing installation: googleapis-common-protos 1.60.0
Uninstalling googleapis-common-protos-1.60.0:
Successfully uninstalled googleapis-common-protos-1.60.0
Attempting uninstall: google-auth
Found existing installation: google-auth 2.22.0
Uninstalling google-auth-2.22.0:
Successfully uninstalled google-auth-2.22.0
Attempting uninstall: grpcio-status
Found existing installation: grpcio-status 1.57.0
Uninstalling grpcio-status-1.57.0:
Successfully uninstalled grpcio-status-1.57.0
Successfully installed Markdown-3.4.3 PyAudio-0.2.13 PyTorch-6.5.1 PyTorch-Qt6-6.5.1 PyTorch-sip-13.5.1 Pygments-2.15.1 QtPy-2.3.1 aiohttp-3.8.4 aiosignal-1.3.1 asttokens-2.2.1 async-timeout-4.0.2 attrs-23.1.0 backcall-0.2.0 certifi-2023.5.7 cffi-1.15.1 charset-normalizer-3.1.0 click-8.1.4 colorama-0.4.6 cryptography-41.0.3 decorator-5.1.1 executing-1.2.0 ffmpeg-1.4 frozenlist-1.3.3 gTTS-2.3.2 google-auth-2.21.0 googleapis-common-protos-1.59.1 grpcio-1.56.0 grpcio-status-1.56.0 idna-3.4 ipython-8.14.0 jedi-0.18.2 joblib-1.3.1 matplotlib-inline-0.1.6 multidict-6.0.4 nltk-3.8.1 numpy-1.25.1 openai-0.27.8 packaging-23.1 pandas-2.0.3 parso-0.8.3 p_ickleshare-0.7.5 prompt-toolkit-3.0.39 protobuf-4.23.4 pure-eval-0.2.2 pycparser-2.21 pydub-0.25.1 pygame-2.5.0 python-dateutil-2.8.2 pytz-2023.3 regex-2023.6.3 requests-2.31.0 soundfile-0.12.1 stack-data-0.6.2 tqdm-4.65.0 traitlets-5.9.0 tzdata-2023.3 urllib3-1.26.16 wcwidth-0.2.6 yarl-1.9.2

```

Figure 5.9: Dependencies Installation during TIAGoGPT Deployment

5.2.5. Configuring API keys

The *openai.ini* file included in the project was edited, with the placeholder content being replaced with the OpenAI API key. This key serves as the gateway to the OpenAI server, while the model version retrieves from the server the appropriate resource needed to process the data. Similarly, the *googlecloud-tts-api.json* file was edited with the placeholder content replaced with the credentials obtained from the Google Cloud account. These credentials are necessary for utilising the *Google Cloud Text – To – Speech* API.

5.2.6. Running the Application

With the environment set up and the necessary configurations in place, TIAGoGPT is now ready to be run. The *TIAGoGPTAppLauncher.py* file is executed to start the TIAGoGPT application as shown in Figure 5.10. Figure 5.11 illustrates conversations between a user and TIAGo robot while, Figure 5.12 showcases TIAGoGPT system performance analysis.

```
python3 TIAGoGPTAppLauncher.py
```


Figure 5.10: TIAGoGPT App Launched during Deployment

Figure 5.11: TIAGoGPT Testing during Deployment

```

cmanex@Ubuntu22: ~/TIAGoGPT
(virt-env) cmanex@Ubuntu22:~/TIAGoGPT$ python3 TIAGoGPTAppLauncher.py
pygame 2.5.0 (SDL 2.28.0, Python 3.10.12)
Hello from the pygame community. https://www.pygame.org/contribute.html
DB Connection Established -----SUCCESS
QSqlDatabasePrivate::removeDatabase: connection 'qt_sql_default_connection' is still in
use, all queries will cease to work.
QSqlDatabasePrivate::addDatabase: duplicate connection name 'qt_sql_default_connection'
, old connection removed.
DB Connection Established -----SUCCESS
Component Initialisation -----SUCCESS
>>Consent Request Form presented

(python3:4752): Gtk-WARNING **: 11:47:33.776: Theme parsing error: <data>:1:0: Expected
a valid selector
>> Consent for Minor indicated
>> Consent given!
Consent saved at 1st location -----SUCCESS
Parameter count mismatch
Consent saved at 2nd location -----SUCCESS
>> Consent Request completed!
Conversation started by TiagoGPT -----SUCCESS
Generated response Synthesised -----SUCCESS
Audio content written to file at resources/audio/synthesized/synthesized_audio_23_08_18
_114847.mp3
ALSA lib pcm_dmix.c:1032:(snd_pcm_dmix_open) unable to open slave
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.rear
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.center_lfe
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.side
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.surround71
ALSA lib setup.c:547:(add_elem) Cannot obtain info for CTL elem (MIXER,'IEC958 Playback
Default',0,0,0): No such file or directory
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.hdmi
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.hdmi
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.modem
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.modem
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.phoneline
ALSA lib pcm.c:2664:(snd_pcm_open_noupdate) Unknown PCM cards.pcm.phoneline
ALSA lib pcm_oss.c:397:(_snd_pcm_oss_open) Cannot open device /dev/dsp
ALSA lib pcm_oss.c:397:(_snd_pcm_oss_open) Cannot open device /dev/dsp
ALSA lib confmisc.c:160:(snd_config_get_card) Invalid field card
ALSA lib pcm_usb_stream.c:482:(_snd_pcm_usb_stream_open) Invalid card 'card'
ALSA lib confmisc.c:160:(snd_config_get_card) Invalid field card
ALSA lib pcm_usb_stream.c:482:(_snd_pcm_usb_stream_open) Invalid card 'card'
ALSA lib pcm_dmix.c:1032:(snd_pcm_dmix_open) unable to open slave
Listening...
Recording started at maximum threshold-----SUCCESS
End of speech detected before the maximum recording duration-----SUCCESS
Recording completed.
output_file: resources/system/temp/recorded_audio_23_08_18_115204.wav
Recorded audio saved as resources/system/temp/recorded_audio_23_08_18_115204.wav -----
-----SUCCESS
Elapsed time: 5.758705377578735 seconds
Audio recording transcribed -----SUCCESS
Response generated by TiagoGPT -----SUCCESS

```

Figure 5.12: TIAGoGPT System Testing during Deployment

6.0 Result Discussion and Challenges

Upon the completion of the different testing carefully performed in the previous chapter, it is important to make some important observations based on the results. Feedback collated during the engagement of both adults and children provided invaluable insights showcased area of strengths and deficiency in the system. This chapter presents the discussion in two perspectives viz: key achievements and the challenges encountered with its proposed solutions.

6.1.Key Achievement

The key achievement is centred on qualitative evaluation approaches adopted which are basically on the accuracy of the transcribed text using the whisper model, the relevance of the response, and the effectiveness of the synthesised text. That is, different set of conversational scenarios were considered during the TIAGoGPT testing phase. It's efficiency and accuracy were gauged with a run down on each response from the GPT model.

As a result, the below figures show the conversation, which in a general context, responded nicely:

6.1.1. Accuracy of Speech Transcription

The text transcribed from speeches was closely compared with the original user-recorded speeches collected during and after the conversation. The result (as seen in figure 6.1 below) showed a significant level of accuracy in capturing and interpreting speeches, with no error detected. However, in a few cases, the system misinterprets; such cases were where the noise-to-signal ratios were considerably higher to represent spoken words and where sounds instead of words were made. The whisper model had difficulties representing sound in text format.

Figure 6.1: Conversation Between TIAGoGPT and the User - (Part 1)

6.1.2. Effectiveness of Synthesised Text

How effective the synthesised texts were was qualitatively evaluated based on clarity in pronunciation and the correctness of the sounding response speech when compared with the generated text response. For a seamless process, and just as shown in the design section of Chapter 4, the generated text was displayed while the synthesised version was played out as audio. The result showed that using the US standard as language during the configuration of the TTS met this goal, as all the users demonstrated great comprehension during the testing phase.

6.1.3. Response Relevance

Although the word count of the response was greatly limited to 12 words at some point, the responses were still tailored and relevant to assist individuals with social skills difficulties. TIAGoGPT was seen

to connect and comfort the user when the user wanted to confide in her by saying, "Of course, feel free to share with me" and "I'm here to listen; what's been bothering you?" in the figure below. In figure 223, it was also seen to make direct, tailored recommendations like social skills activities, role play, and conversation practice. In another scenario, TIAGoGPT did a role play of a doctor and patient with a detailed conversation.

Figure 6.2: Conversation Between TIAGoGPT and the User - (Part 2)

6.2. Challenges and Issues with TIAGoGPT

Aside from the issues noted in the above sections, the challenges in TIAGoGPT implementation and deployment are discussed as follows:

6.2.1. Technical and Functional Issues

Cases of system anomalies such as coding errors, integration errors, and others causing undesired outputs were noted and a greater percentage of them were detected during development and the deployment phases of the TIAGoGPT system. In some other instance, the response delay timer used between the TTS and next interaction phase to avoid interferences from different processes during interactions were identified as problematic. These increased the wait time undesirably. Through serial testing, the timer was nicely adjusted.

6.2.2. Compatibility Issues

Although the TIAGoGPT was successfully deployed as explained in the previous chapter, its deployment was not on the TIAGo robot itself as expected but was still within an environment with similar specifications set out in Chapter 3. Compatibility issues with the robot were a major setback. The robot system requirements were far below the recommended, and with 51GB of HDD, 1GB of RAM, and dual-core processor system resources, Ubuntu 16.04 LTS, and Python 3.5, nothing could be achieved.

6.2.3. Legal, Social, Ethical, and Professional Issues (LSEPI)

The LSEPI, which covers a broad area of issues, is discussed as follows:

1. Data Security and Privacy Concerns

The LSEP issues raise concerns around data collection, processing, privacy, and security. This section is very vital to this project as users' data (spoken words) was collected, stored, and processed during the interaction period with the TIAGoGPT. To ensure that user data was collected and processed within the permissible corridors of this research, a set of data protection frameworks were implemented. One of them is the use of an explicit and well-worded consent form implemented and integrated into the system. As part of the process, data anonymization using hash technology was used to protect users' privacy. On the user data storage, several actions were taken, viz., file access controls, data encryptions, and secure deletion of the data, which served as an added layer of security to the data. All these were used throughout the user-interacting period with the system.

However, it is worthy to note that for the secure deletion of the data, techniques were adopted as an efficient control measure (aside from physically destroying the storage location), and the data was overwritten before finally being destroyed. The destruction period is within 24 hours from when the data was collected. Also, as a backup implementation, on system start, a check is performed to ensure that there is no undeleted data left within the system.

2. Ethical and Social Considerations

Despite the exceptional performance recorded on the generated responses tested on a wide range of input cases, it was still observed (as evidenced in Figure 6.2 above) that TIAGoGPT

could hallucinate inconsistent, inaccurate information with possible biases; therefore, as best practices, it is highly recommended that users' expectations are calibrated appropriately and constantly monitored to avoid litigation and unsafe responses.

3. Legal and Professional Considerations

Borrowed codes from third-party sources such as repositories and open-source libraries used in the system TIAGoGPT implementation were meticulously considered in accordance with the professional conduct. The associated terms of use, licenses, and other relevant risk associated with their use were correctly interpreted and acted upon accordingly.

6.2.4. Unforeseen Edge Cases

This section is set as a reminder that, as much as issues were identified with possible solutions provided, there is a need to exercise due diligence in using, directly or indirectly, and as a whole or in part, the TIAGoGPT system. There could be certain scenarios that could potentially reveal the vulnerabilities that were not initially recorded, as this is a research project and not suitable for real-world adoption.

7.0 Conclusion and Future Perspective

7.1. Conclusion

This project presents a comprehensive solution leveraging cutting-edge technology to address the needs of children with social skill difficulties. The combination of LLMs like GPT-3.5-Turbo and Whisper with the TIAGo robot not only showcased its technical innovation but also provided personalized, interactive, and effective interventions, showing a great commitment to enhancing the lives of children with social skill difficulties. Multiple modules, including voice recording and processing, voice transcription using the Whisper model, response generation using GPT-3.5-Turbo, text synthesis via GoogleCloud TTS, and a dual conversation mode that supports both text-based and voice-based interactions, were implemented. The system ensured secure data storage, access control, and data anonymization that addressed data privacy concerns. It also implemented audit logs, consent management, and a data security framework to safeguard sensitive information.

In conclusion, the project holds immense promise for revolutionizing how children with social skill difficulties receive support and interventions. The integration of LLMs and robotics offers a dynamic, responsive, and personalized approach that can adapt to individual needs and foster improved social interactions. Throughout the development and deployment phases, rigorous testing and refining were conducted to ensure the clarity of speech, accuracy of transcription, effectiveness of text synthesis, and tailored responses to users' unique requirements. Challenges related to module integration, system response times, and seamless API interaction were identified and addressed through comprehensive testing strategies.

7.2. Suggestions and Future Perspectives

The project is a significant step forward in utilising technology to assist children with social skill difficulties. As the project moves forward, there are several suggestions and areas for future improvement that can enhance its effectiveness and impact:

While the project effectively integrates LLMs and robotics, exploring further multi-modal integration, such as incorporating social cues, gesture recognition, facial expression, and speech pattern analysis, could provide more holistic and nuanced interactions. This could lead to a deeper understanding of user emotions and needs, enabling even more tailored responses. Implementing a mechanism for the system to adapt and personalise interventions over a long-term period could enhance its effectiveness. The system could dynamically adjust its responses and suggestions to cater to individual growth by analysing user interactions and progress.

The system's potential effects may also be felt by other populations, such as those with ASD, ADHD, NVLD, or even those learning a new language, even though the project's primary audience is young

children who struggle with social skills. This could broaden their reach by considering diverse user needs. Also, within the children's context, tailoring interventions for specific age groups within the children's range can enhance the relevance and effectiveness of the system's interactions.

Furthermore, moving beyond the research and development phase to piloting the system in real-world environments, such as schools or therapy centres, can provide valuable insights into its practical application and specific user acceptance. Feedback from users and professionals can guide further improvements. It is also important to state that as AI and robotics become more integrated into human life, a focus on ethical considerations becomes paramount. Continuously updating the system to ensure transparency, fairness, and unbiased responses is essential to maintaining user trust and avoiding unintended consequences.

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